

Preparation of CdSe/ZnS_xO_{1-x} core/shell quantum dots by controlled oxidation of ZnS shell.

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ABSTRACT: Core/shell nanocrystals (NCs) with chalcogenide core and ZnO shell are a class of materials with a potential for application in optoelectronics, bioimaging, photocatalysis and other areas. However, the preparation of these nano-heterostructures is challenging because of the large lattice mismatch between the chalcogenide and ZnO crystal lattices. Here we describe a previously unexplored approach to preparation of spherical CdSe/ZnO core/shell nano-heterostructures based on controlled oxidation of ZnS shell of CdS/ZnS NCs. We show that exposure of CdSe/ZnS NCs suspended in octadecene to oxygen at 120 °C leads to gradual (over ~2 hrs.) oxidation of the ZnS to ZnS_xO_{1-x} with high oxygen content. At longer times the exposure to oxygen leads to the degradation of the CdSe-ZnS interface and oxidation of the CdSe core. The described method paves the way for the exploration of the chalcogenide/ZnO nano-heterostructures in applications.

INTRODUCTION

Size- and shape-tunability of electronic properties resulting from the quantum confinement effect make colloidal semiconductor nanocrystals (NCs) an attractive class of materials for exploitation in a broad range of innovative technologies in areas including optoelectronics, bioimaging, quantum information technologies and many others.¹⁻⁹ However, due to the high surface-to-volume ratio of NCs, one of the challenges in the development of applications is the control of the properties of the NC surfaces. Defects in the structure of the NC surface, often introduced during the NC synthesis, can form charge carriers trap states, accelerate nonradiative recombination, and reduce chemical stability of the NCs. Core/shell architectures represent one possible approach for overcoming this challenge as they commonly lead to improved passivation of the surface states, control over carrier localization and interfacial electronic properties. Semiconductor shells with compositions such as ZnS, CdS, and ZnSe have been extensively

investigated in this context.¹⁰⁻¹¹ However, these conventional semiconductor shell materials often from limited chemical stability and restricted functionality beyond the optical passivation. Consequently, the exploration of alternative shell materials, particularly metal oxides, has emerged as an important direction in colloidal nanocrystal research.

Zinc oxide (ZnO) represents a particularly attractive shell material because of its combination of wide band gap (~3.3 eV),¹² conduction band onset similar to CdSe,¹³⁻¹⁴ high carrier mobilities,¹⁵ chemical robustness, low toxicity and optical transparency. As a result, unlike conventional insulating oxide coatings such as SiO₂, in nano-heterostructures ZnO can directly participate in charge delocalization and charge transfer processes. Thus, ZnO shells can provide not only environmental protection, surface passivation and reduction in toxicity but also additional pathways for electron transport, charge separation, and interfacial energy transfer. These properties make ZnO-containing core/shell nanocrystals promising candidates for applications in photocatalysis, solar-energy conversion, light emission, sensing, and hybrid optoelectronic systems.

Some of the early reports on preparation of core/shell structures with ZnO shell utilized hydrothermal approach for the shell formation.¹⁶⁻¹⁷ Compared to hydrothermal approaches, colloidal synthesis provides several advantages, such as access to discrete core/shell nanoparticles, better control over the size of the NCs, shell thickness, composition and surface and interface chemistry, which are essential for understanding nanoscale charge transport and exciton dynamics. Earlier reports on colloidal CdTe/CdS/ZnO¹⁸ and CdSe/ZnO¹⁹ quantum dots and CdSe/ZnO nanorods²⁰ established the feasibility of preparing such structures by colloidal approach. The analysis of the prepared materials showed that introduction of ZnO shell leads to enhanced photoluminescence efficiency and improved resistance against photochemical degradation.¹⁸⁻¹⁹ The studies have also revealed that ZnO can modify localization of carriers in the excited state, promote charge separation, and introduce new interfacial phenomena that are

Figure 1. Scheme of the synthetic approach used in preparation of the CdSe/ZnS_xO_{1-x} core/shell quantum dots

inaccessible in traditional semiconductor-shell systems.^{18, 20} Despite these advances, the synthesis of colloidal core/shell NCs with well-defined ZnO-shell remains much less developed compared to established ZnS- or CdS-based shell systems. Fundamental challenges remain in controlling shell composition, crystallinity, thickness, interface defects, and the balance between heterogeneous shell growth and homogeneous ZnO nucleation.

In previous reports on ZnO shells prepared by colloidal method the shells were prepared by reaction of preformed “core” NCs with reagents such as zinc acetylacetonate ($\text{Zn}(\text{Acac})_2$), which served as a source of Zn and oxygen. As noted above, a challenge of this approach is the tendency of ZnO monomers formed by thermal decomposition of $\text{Zn}(\text{Acac})_2$ to form an independent population of ZnO nanocrystals instead of ZnO shell. This is a particular problem in cases where there is large lattice mismatch between the crystal structure of the core (e.g., ~24-26% in case of CdSe/ZnO). In such cases, preparation of quality ZnO shell is challenging even with approaches, such as SILAR where the Zn precursor (e.g., $\text{Zn}(\text{Et})_2$) and oxygen precursor (e.g., oxygen, alcohol) are added sequentially, to prevent the formation of independent ZnO population. In this work we describe an alternative approach to preparation of CdSe/ZnO core/shell structures based on controlled oxidation of ZnS shell in CdSe/ZnS core/shell structures. Although controlled oxidation of ZnS to ZnO was investigated,²¹⁻²² it has not been applied to CdSe/ZnS nano-heterostructures. The approach is schematically summarized in Figure 1. In this approach the CdSe/ZnS heterostructures are prepared by standard approaches reported previously. These heterostructures are then exposed to oxygen under controlled conditions (temperature, O_2 pressure, reaction time). We find that under well-defined conditions the ZnS shell can be partially or completely converted into the ZnO, without significantly affecting the chemical composition or size of the CdSe core. The effect of the chemical conversion of the shell on the optical properties of the nano-heterostructures is analyzed and discussed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Materials syntheses. The core CdSe QDs were synthesized by literature procedure.¹⁹ Briefly, Cd-oleate was reacted with a Se-TOP-TMPPA precursor solution at high temperature, and growth was monitored by absorption spectroscopy until cores reached 6–6.5 nm. The ZnS shell was grown by a modified low-temperature, single-precursor method.²³ Briefly, zinc diethyldithiocarbamate ($\text{Zn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_2$) served as a single molecule source for Zn, and S. More details are provided in the experimental section.

Oxidation of CdSe/ZnS NCs. For the oxidation of NCs, previously prepared CdSe/ZnS core/shell nano-heterostructures were washed with an excess of acetone and methanol and dissolved in hexanes, then subsequently transferred into a 25 mL three-neck flask equipped with rubber septa and a condenser, connected to a Schlenk line with a vacuum hose. To remove the air and moisture the apparatus was evacuated and filled with argon three times at room temperature and subsequently three more times at 80 °C. A needle connected to a balloon filled with pure oxygen was inserted through the rubber septum into the flask containing the CdSe/ZnS NCs under argon, exposing the NCs solution to a slight positive pressure of oxygen. The temperature was increased to 120 °C to initiate oxidation. To monitor the progress of the oxidation, small aliquots (~100 μL) of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at regular intervals (typically every 15 min.). The optical properties, structure, and chemical composition of the aliquots and the final product were characterized, as described below. For the control experiments, the CdSe/ZnS NCs were subjected to the same washing procedure and thermal treatment under argon instead of an oxygen atmosphere.

Monitoring of the oxidation by optical spectroscopy. Figure 2 summarizes the result of the monitoring of the oxidation of CdSe/ZnS NCs by UVVIS absorption (panels a, b) and photoluminescence (PL) (panels c, d) spectroscopies and pPL relaxation

Figure 2. Changes in the electronic absorption (a), photoluminescence (c) and excited state lifetimes (e) observed during the exposure of CdSe/ZnS NCs to O_2 at 120 °C for 240 min. Panels (b), (d) and (e) show the summary of the results as shown in (a), (c) and (e) for the CdSe/ZnS NCs to O_2 at 120 °C (red symbols) compared with the changes observed for the CdSe/ZnS “control” sample subjected to the same heating program under Ar atmosphere (black symbols). The results for CdSe core are included as gray symbols. In panel (d) the filled symbols refer to PL peak position and empty symbols refer to PL peak intensity. In panel (f) the $\langle \tau \rangle$ refers to average excited state lifetime obtained by fitting of a multiexponential expression to the PL relaxation dynamics showed in panel (a) and similar results for the “control” sample. All experimental measurements were performed at room temperature on NCs suspended in hexanes.

dynamics measurements (panels e, f). The results show the evolution of the optical features of the CdSe/ZnS NCs exposed to oxygen for period of 240 minutes and a control sample of the same batch of NCs subjected to the same thermal treatment under argon atmosphere for the same period of time. Optical properties of the CdSe cores are included for comparison.

Inspection of the absorption spectra shown in panel (a) reveals that for the CdSe/ZnS NCs, exposed to oxygen at 120 °C, the position of the 1s peak near 630 nm remains unchanged for the first 120 min. However, at 240 min. the 1s peak (and the entire spectrum of the NCs) clearly shifts to shorter wavelengths. These observations are more quantitatively summarized in Fig. 3b, which shows the position of the 1s peak for CdSe core (gray symbol) and the positions of the 1s peak for CdSe/ZnS heated to 120 °C under argon (black symbols) and oxygen (red symbols), as a function of heating time. The results indicate that the position of 1s peak of the CdSe core and CdSe/ZnS core/shell NCs prior to heating are the same at 627 nm; i.e., overcoating of the CdSe core with the ZnS shell did not affect the position of the 1s peak. Upon heating under Argon, the peak position of the CdSe/ZnS NCs stays the same for the first 30 min. and then it shifts to longer wavelengths, 629 and 628 nm after 120 and 240 min., respectively. In contrast, for CdSe/ZnS exposed to oxygen, peak position remains unchanged at 627 nm for the first 120 min. and then it shifts to shorter wavelength by 5 nm to 622 nm.

Panel (c) summarizes the changes in the PL observed for the CdSe/ZnS NCs, exposed to oxygen at 120 °C for 240 min. The results show that the PL intensity shows about 5% increase in the first 30 min., followed by about 15% decrease after 120 min. and more than 90% decrease in intensity after 240 min. At the same time, within the first 120 min., the PL peak shows slight red shift, followed by a significant blue shift. These observations are more quantitatively summarized in panel (d) together with the corresponding results for the “control” CdSe/ZnS NC sample exposed to argon and the results obtained for the CdSe core. The comparison shows that while the PL intensity of the “control” sample (black empty symbols) monotonously increases over time, which is in sharp contrast with the CdSe/ZnS NC sample exposed to oxygen (red empty symbols). The position of the PL peak for the oxygen exposed sample within the first 30 and 120 min. shifts to 647 and

645 nm, respectively. At 240 min the peak shifts in opposite direction relative to untreated NCs, to 640 nm. In contrast, the “control” sample does not show significant shift in the peak PL peak position during the monitored 240 min.

Panel (e) shows the changes in the PL relaxation dynamics observed for the CdSe/ZnS NCs, exposed to oxygen, compared with the PL relaxation dynamics of the CdSe core. The results show that overcoating of the CdSe core with ZnS shell leads to a clear reduction in the relaxation dynamics. This is attributed to an effective passivation of the nonradiative relaxation channels associated with surface defects in the CdSe cores by the ZnS shell, as was described in many earlier studies. Following the exposure of the CdSe/ZnS NCs to oxygen, no significant variation in the PL relaxation dynamics is observed for the first 120 min. However, at 240 min. the relaxation dynamics becomes much faster, very similar to the CdSe core. These observations are more quantitatively summarized in panel (f) (red symbols) together with the results obtained for the “control” sample exposed to argon. The procedure used to extract the average lifetime from the PL intensity decays is described in the methods section. The results show that the average lifetime shows a monotonous increase over the entire monitored time for the “control” sample. In contrast, for the oxygen exposed NCs the average lifetime varies slightly over the first 120 min. and then sharply decreases at 240 min. The observed variations in the average lifetime for both samples correlate closely with the variations in the PL intensities shown in panel (d) as empty symbols.

We interpret the results of the optical studies as follows. The CdSe/ZnS NCs heated under Ar atmosphere (“control”) exhibit negligible changes in the position of the 1s absorption peak near 627 nm and only minor variations in the energy of the PL peak position and intensity and PL relaxation dynamics. This indicates that thermal treatment alone does not significantly alter the NC structure. Small, gradual increase in the PL intensity and average lifetime are attributed to heating-induced surface ligands and atoms rearrangement and thermal relaxation, reducing in better passivation of surface defects. In contrast, exposure to oxygen resulted in distinct time-dependent changes. During the first 120 min of oxidation, the 1s absorption peak remained essentially unchanged, indicating preservation of the CdSe core size and quantum confinement. However, the initial PL peak shift from 640 to 646 nm

Figure 3. HAADF STEM images of (a) CdSe (b) CdSe/ZnS and (c) CdSe/ZnS_xO_{1-x} nanocrystals prepared by the approach shown in Fig. 1. Panels (d-f) show corresponding histograms generated by statistical analysis of at least one hundred NCs in each sample.

accompanied by an increase in average excited-state lifetime from ~15 to ~18 ns, suggests modification of the electronic coupling between the CdSe core and the surrounding shell. These changes are consistent with the early-stage ZnS shell oxidation, resulting in formation of a partially oxidized $\text{ZnS}_x\text{O}_{1-x}$ shell and/or altered interfacial dielectric environment, which reduces electron-hole overlap, without substantial perturbation of the CdSe core.

At longer oxidation times, between 120 and 240 min, the significant shift of the 1s absorption peak (627 to 622 nm), accompanied by a pronounced blue shift of the PL emission (644 to 640 nm) and a substantial reduction in PL intensity, indicate progressive deterioration of the CdSe core. Concurrently, the decrease in the average lifetime decreased from ~15 ns to ~7.6 ns, indicates emergence of additional nonradiative recombination pathways. These observations suggest that prolonged oxygen exposure leads to degradation of the CdSe/ZnS interface, followed by structural modification of the CdSe core. Thus, the optical measurements indicate a two-stage oxidation process: an initial regime dominated by ZnS shell modification while maintaining CdSe core integrity, followed by a secondary regime characterized by interface and core degradation. The results identify the intermediate oxidation window (approximately 30–120 min under the present conditions) as the most favorable regime for generating partially oxidized ZnS-derived shells while preserving the optical properties of the CdSe core.

High-Resolution Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (HR-STEM). Panels (a)-(c) in Figure 3 show the High-Angle Annular Dark Field (HAADF) STEM images of the prepared CdSe cores, CdSe/ZnS core/shell structures before and after exposure to oxygen atmosphere. Panels (d)-(f) show the corresponding NCs size distribution histograms. The results show that the average size of the CdSe core nanocrystals is 6.2 nm and increases to about 7.7 nm after the growth of the ZnS shell. This size increase of ~1.5 nm is consistent with formation of 2 monolayers (ML) of ZnS shell (about 0.62 nm for a single ML²³). The image of the core/shell NCs (panel (b)) shows clear atomic columns across the particle, indicating that the NCs retain good crystallinity during the ZnS shell growth. After the 2 hrs. of oxygen exposure, the average size of

NCs remains virtually unchanged at ~7.5 nm (panels (e) and (f)), which indicates that the oxidation did not lead to significant shell etching, dissolution, or additional shell growth. This is consistent with earlier studies of anion exchange reactions in semiconductor NCs,²⁴⁻²⁵ which showed that during the anion exchange reactions the parent NC largely retains its size and shape. This is in contrast with cation-exchange processes, where the ion exchange typically leads to the rearrangement of the crystal lattice.²⁶ To gain further insights into the changes induced by the exposure of CdSe/ZnS to oxidizing atmosphere the NCs were analyzed by Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS), as described in the following paragraphs.

Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS). Electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) is a STEM-based technique that provides spatially resolved chemical information at the nanoscale by analyzing the energy lost by transmitted electrons as they pass through the sample.²⁷ Because the electron probe can be positioned with sub-nanometer precision, it can both map-out where elements sit within a single core/shell nanocrystal and quantify their relative atomic composition. This makes it a useful tool for confirming shell formation and picking up on compositional changes that might not show up as a change in particle size.²⁸⁻²⁹ Figure 4 shows the STEM images and elemental EELS maps for Cd, Se, O, S, and Zn in the CdSe core, CdSe/ZnS core/shell, and CdSe/ZnS_xO_{1-x} (oxidized) samples. The corresponding atomic % composition for each element, normalized to Cd, are summarized in Table 1.

For the bare CdSe core, the Cd and Se maps overlap strongly across the entire particle, which is what is expected for NCs with high crystallinity. The oxygen map shows only weak, scattered signal with low correlation with the particle shape. We attribute the weak oxygen signal primarily to surface ligands (e.g. TMPPA) and/or partial surface contamination rather than an actual oxide phase.³⁰ The results in Table 1 supports this conclusion as the Cd:Se ratio is close to 1 (9.5:10.6 at. %), and oxygen is essentially undetectable (0 at. %). Thus, we conclude that the CdSe core is oxide-free before the ZnS shell growth.

Figure 4. EELS spectra of the CdSe (top row), CdSe/ZnS (middle row) CdSe/ZnS_xO_{1-x} (bottom row) nanocrystals prepared by the approach shown in Fig. 1. In the color element mapping Cd (M-edge), Se (L-edge), Zn (L-edge), S (L-edge) and O (K-edge) are indicated by purple, cyan, green, blue and yellow colors, respectively.

Table 1. Elemental composition of CdSe, CdSe/ZnS, CdSe/ZnSO Nanocrystals determined by EELS. For each element (Cd, Se, Zn, S, O, C), the values are composition in atomic % (composition normalized relative to Cd).^a

Sample	Cd	Se	Zn	S	O	C
CdSe core	9.5 ± 1.8 (1.0)	10.6 ± 1.1 (1.11)	-	-	0	80.0 ± 1.9 (8.42)
CdSe/ZnS	4.9 ± 0.9 (1.0)	5.7 ± 0.6 (1.16)	3.7 ± 0.4 (0.75)	4.9 ± 0.5 (1.0)	0	80.9 ± 1.3 (16.5)
CdSe/ZnS _x O _{1-x}	2.0 ± 0.4 (1.0)	2.8 ± 0.3 (1.4)	3.5 ± 0.4 (1.75)	2.9 ± 0.3 (1.45)	4.0 ± 0.3 (2.0)	84.8 ± 0.9 (42.2)

^aThe strong signal for C is attributed to the carbon film on TEM grid and organic ligands on the surface of NCs.

Following the ZnS shell growth, the Cd and Se signal stays concentrated in the core region, complemented by signals for Zn and S observed in the same core region. This indicates successful formation of a uniform ZnS shell around the CdSe core, in line with earlier EELS studies of the CdSe/ZnS core/shell NCs [888, 999]. Signal for oxygen is also weak and featureless here, just like in the core sample, indicating that the ZnS shell growth does not introduce significant amount of oxygen into the heterostructure. As shown in Table 1: Zn (3.7 at. %) and S (4.9 at. %) are both clearly present, with a Zn:S ratio close to 1:1, as expected for ZnS crystal. Concurrently, the oxygen amount is observed still at ~0 at. %.

For the oxidized CdSe/ZnS_xO_{1-x} sample, the signals for Cd and Se are still confined to the core, indicating that the core is not significantly affected by the oxidation. However, the oxygen signal now clearly spatially overlaps with the particle position, with the strongest signal overlapping spatially with the Zn signal in on the surface of the NCs. Oxygen is thus present primarily in the shell, rather than as a separate region, suggesting a shell-confined compositional exchange. The results in Table 1 support this conclusion more quantitatively: in the particle region the oxygen content increases to a clearly measurable 4.0 atomic % (compared to 0 in the other two samples), and the Zn:S ratio increases from 0.76 in CdSe/ZnS to 1.21 in CdSe/ZnS_xO_{1-x}, which corresponds to ~63% reduction in S content. At the same time, the measured O:S ratio in the oxidized sample is 1.38, i.e., ~40% excess of oxygen over sulfur. These results indicate that in the studied sample, at least 40-60% of sulfur was successfully replaced with oxygen, forming mixed-anion ZnS_{1-x}O_x-type shell around the CdSe core.

XRD analysis. Figure 5 shows the results of the XRD analysis of the drop-cast films of the CdSe, CdSe/ZnS and CdSe/ZnS_xO_{1-x} NCs. The bare CdSe core shows diffraction pattern consistent with the wurtzite structure reported earlier.³¹ Following the growth of the ZnS shell, the diffraction peak near 25° shows a clear additional shoulder at 28.5°, which we attribute to the (111) diffraction peak of the zinc blende ZnS. Furthermore, the peaks associated with the (110) and (103)/(112) planes of CdSe wurtzite became sharper and more clearly resolved relative to the core spectrum, which is attributed to lattice strain introduced by a thin ZnS shell layer deposited on the CdSe core.³² No significant shift of the core diffraction peaks toward the bulk ZnS peak positions was observed, which is expected for a thin shell of only one to two ZnS monolayers. The reason can be that the lattice mismatch in the CdSe/ZnS core/shell interface produces a modest peak shift at low shell thicknesses.³³ Overall, the peak sharpening observed after shell growth and no substantial peak shift to the bulk ZnS positions are consistent with a thin epitaxial ZnS shell formation on the CdSe core surface. When comparing the diffraction patterns of the freshly prepared CdSe/ZnS (red trace) and oxidized CdSe/ZnS (blue trace), we note a decrease in the signal near 28.5° attributed to the diffraction from the ZnS (111) plane. However, the differences in the diffraction angles with the strongest expected diffractions of ZnO, 36.5° (101) or 57° (110) are at the edge of detectability. Therefore, we conclude that the ZnS_xO_{1-x} does not form a well-defined crystal phase.

CONCLUSIONS

We have shown that exposure of CdSe/ZnS core/shell nanocrystals to oxygen, under controlled conditions can be used to modify the ZnS shell to a shell with composition ZnS_xO_{1-x}, with a majority oxygen content. The gradual oxidation of the shell can be effectively monitored by combination of UVVIS absorption and photoluminescence spectroscopies. The results show that under conditions where CdSe/ZnS NCs suspended in octadecene are exposed to a small overpressure of oxygen and heated to 120 °C, the full conversion of the ZnS shell to ZnS_xO_{1-x} takes about two hours. Further exposure to oxygen under these conditions leads to degradation of the CdSe core. The XRD analysis suggests that the mixed oxide shell is likely amorphous. Overall, the presented method represents a new possible approach for preparation of core/shell nanostructures with oxide shells.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. Cadmium oxide (CdO, 99.95%, Sigma-Alfa Aesar), selenium powder (Se, 99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich), oylamine (OAm, technical grade 70%, Sigma-Aldrich), oleic acid (OA, 90% Sigma Aldrich), 1-octadecene (ODE, technical grade 90%, Sigma Aldrich), *n*-hexane (95%, Emplura), trioctylphosphine (TOP, 97%,

Figure 5. XRD patterns for CdSe and CdSe/ZnS NCs and the CdSe/ZnS exposed to oxygen for 2 hrs. The bottom three panels show the reference patterns for the ZnO (wurtzite), ZnS (Zinc blende) and CdSe (wurtzite) based on ICDD database.

Sigma-Aldrich), Bis(2,2,4-trimethylpentyl) phosphinic acid (TMPPA, 90%, Ambeed), Zinc diethyldithiocarbamate ($\text{Zn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_2$, 99%, TCI), acetone (99.5%, Mikrochem), chloroform (99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich), methanol (99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich), oxygen (99.9%, Messer) were all used as received from the supplier, without further purification.

Synthesis of CdSe NCs. The CdSe cores were synthesized by modified literature procedure.¹⁹ Cadmium oleate was prepared by loading CdO (0.935 mmol), OA (5.59 mmol), and 15 g of ODE into a three-neck round-bottom flask, degassing it at 80 °C for 1 hour in an inert atmosphere, and then heating it to 310 °C. Transparent cadmium oleate solution was formed at this temperature. Then, a selenium precursor solution containing Se (2.14 mmol), TOP (3.7 mmol), TMPPA (2.57 mmol), OAM (2.78 mmol), and 1.65 g ODE was swiftly injected to the reaction flask at 310 °C. After that, the reaction temperature was kept at 230 °C to encourage the formation of CdSe nanocrystals. Absorption spectroscopy was used to track the size of the nanocrystals during the reaction, and once the target size (6 to 6.5 nm) was reached, the growth process was stopped by removing the flask from the heating source. Excess of ligands and by products were removed to purify the resultant CdSe nanocrystals using a combination of acetone, methanol, and chloroform. The purified NCs were dissolved in n-hexane and kept in cold and dark storing place for further reactions and characterizations.

Synthesis of CdSe/ZnS NCs. CdSe/ZnS core/shell NCs were prepared by modified procedure originally reported by Dethlefsen et al.²³ Single molecular precursor zinc diethyldithiocarbamate ($\text{Zn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_2$) was used as both Zn and S elemental source. The amount of $\text{Zn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_2$ required for depositing 2 monolayers of ZnS shell layer on CdSe core material was calculated by the standard geometric stoichiometry method [2]. Synthesis procedure Briefly, 100 nmol of purified CdSe cores in 10 mL of octadecene - 1 (ODE), 3 mL of oleylamine (OLA), and 80.6 mg (0.223 mmol) of crystalline $\text{Zn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_2$ were loaded into a three-necked round-bottom flask (25 mL). The mixture was degassed at 70 °C for 1 h. Then 3 mL tri-n-octylphosphine (TOP) was transferred and injected into the flask containing the reaction mixture. The reaction mixture was heated slowly (2 °C/min) to 110–120 °C under a nitrogen atmosphere and kept at this temperature for 2 h, then the mixture was cooled to room temperature. The core/shell nanocrystals were precipitated by sequential addition of 25 mL 1-butanol, 20 mL acetone and 20 mL methanol, separated by centrifugation and washed with 20 mL 1-butanol and 20 mL methanol, and finally dissolved in n-hexane.

HR-STEM measurements. Structural and elemental analysis was carried out using an aberration-corrected analytical transmission electron microscope JEM-ARM200cF (JEOL) operated at 200 kV. For STEM imaging, the probe convergence semi-angle was set to 22.3 mrad. High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector's inner and outer semi-angles were 54 and 220 mrad, respectively.

EELS measurements. EELS elemental analysis was done using a Gatan GIF 965 Quantum ER camera equipped with a fast-Dual EELS system. EELS collection semi-angle was to 29.3 mrad. The energy dispersion was set at 1 eV/channel. All acquired data were processed with 64-bit Digital Micrograph GMS 3.61 (Gatan). The NCs dispersed in n-hexane solution were drop-casted on ultra-thin carbon TEM grid (400 mesh Cu) followed by IR lamp drying.

Absorption spectroscopy. Absorption spectra of n-hexane solutions of MoS_2 NPLs were collected using Agilent 8453 diode-array spectrometer using 1 cm quartz cells.

Photoluminescence spectroscopy. The photoluminescence spectra were recorded using a Fluoromax 3 plus C, spectrofluorometer (Horiba) equipped with ae Hamamatsu R13456 red-sensitive photomultiplier tube.

Time-resolved photoluminescence. The time-resolved PL decays were collected using a time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) Delta Diode system (Horiba) using a pulsed laser diode (402 nm) with the repetition rate of 1 MHz, pump power 50 μW and probe beam diameter of 1 mm. The FWHM of the instrument response function was 50 ps. The NCs were dispersed in n-hexane and all the spectra were collected in solution. The PL decays were analyzed by fitting a multiexponential expression shown in Eq. (1) to the experimental data.

$$I(t) = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \exp(-\tau_i/t) \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1) a_i and τ_i are the relative contribution and the life-time of i -th component, respectively. The average lifetimes were calculated by the expression shown in Eq. (2).

$$\langle \tau \rangle = \frac{\sum_i^n a_i \tau_i^2}{\sum_i^n a_i \tau_i} \quad (2)$$

X-ray diffraction spectroscopy. The crystalline phases present in the drop-cast films of the NCs were identified using X-ray diffraction (XRD) (Panalytical Empyrean, Netherlands, Cu $K\alpha$ radiation). Rietveld analysis for quantitative analysis and lattice parameters determination was done using HighScore Plus on scans with 2θ ranging from 15° to 70° with a step of 0.026°.

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Author Contributions

E.R.A.: Conceptualization, materials synthesis, characterization, data analysis, visualization, manuscript writing, manuscript editing. V.V.: Materials characterization, data analysis, visualization, manuscript writing, manuscript editing. M.S.: Conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration, original manuscript writing, data analysis, visualization, editing. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

There are no conflicts to declare.

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REFERENCES

- (1) Talapin, D. V., et al., Prospects of Colloidal Nanocrystals for Electronic and Optoelectronic Applications. *Chem. Rev.* **2010**, *110* (1), 389-458.
- (2) Wilker, M. B., et al., Recent Progress in Photocatalysis Mediated by Colloidal II-VI Nanocrystals. *Isr. J. Chem.* **2012**, *52* (11-12), 1002-1015.
- (3) Kairdolf, B. A., et al., Semiconductor Quantum Dots for Bioimaging and Bodiagnostic Applications. *Annual Review of Analytical Chemistry* **2013**, *6* (Volume 6, 2013), 143-162.
- (4) Kershaw, S. V., et al., Materials aspects of semiconductor nanocrystals for optoelectronic applications. *Materials Horizons* **2017**, *4* (2), 155-205.
- (5) Li, X.-B., et al., Semiconductor nanocrystals for small molecule activation via artificial photosynthesis. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2020**, *49* (24), 9028-9056.
- (6) Kagan, C. R., et al., Colloidal Quantum Dots as Platforms for Quantum Information Science. *Chem. Rev.* **2021**, *121* (5), 3186-3233.

- (7) García de Arquer, F. P., et al., Semiconductor quantum dots: Technological progress and future challenges. *Science* **2021**, *373* (6555), eaaz8541.
- (8) Vajner, D. A., et al., Quantum Communication Using Semiconductor Quantum Dots. *Advanced Quantum Technologies* **2022**, *5* (7), 2100116.
- (9) Tsui, E. Y., Surface Considerations in Colloidal Semiconductor Nanocrystal Photocatalysis: A Mini Review. *Energy & Fuels* **2025**, *39* (15), 7182-7195.
- (10) Reiss, P., et al., Core/Shell Semiconductor Nanocrystals. *Small* **2009**, *5* (2), 154-168.
- (11) Ghosh Chaudhuri, R.; Paria, S., Core/Shell Nanoparticles: Classes, Properties, Synthesis Mechanisms, Characterization, and Applications. *Chem. Rev.* **2012**, *112* (4), 2373-2433.
- (12) Srikant, V.; Clarke, D. R., On the optical band gap of zinc oxide. *J. Appl. Phys.* **1998**, *83* (10), 5447-5451.
- (13) Carlson, B., et al., Valence Band Alignment at Cadmium Selenide Quantum Dot and Zinc Oxide (10 $\bar{1}$ 0) Interfaces. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2008**, *112* (22), 8419-8423.
- (14) Li, R., et al., Band alignment of ZnO/CdSe quantum dots heterojunction determined by ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy using synchrotron radiation. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2013**, *276*, 258-261.
- (15) Makino, T., et al., Electron transport in ZnO thin films. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2005**, *87* (2).
- (16) Yan, C., et al., Preparation of CdS/ZnO Core/shell Structured Nanoparticles by Hydrothermal Method. *MRS Online Proceedings Library* **2011**, *692* (1), 9411.
- (17) Chen, X. L., et al., Hydrothermal-based synthesis of CdS/ZnO quantum dots. *Advanced Materials Research* **2014**, *875*, 362-365.
- (18) Aldeek, F., et al., Enhanced Optical Properties of Core/Shell/Shell CdTe/CdS/ZnO Quantum Dots Prepared in Aqueous Solution. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2009**, *113* (45), 19458-19467.
- (19) Nguyen, T. L., et al., Synthesis of Highly Crystalline CdSe@ZnO Nanocrystals via Monolayer-by-Monolayer Epitaxial Shell Deposition. *Chem. Mater.* **2014**, *26* (14), 4274-4279.
- (20) Haque, A., et al., Type-II CdSe/ZnO core/shell nanorods: nanoheterostructures with a tunable dual emission in visible and near-infrared spectral ranges. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2024**, *34* (16), 2305296.
- (21) Dengo, N., et al., Thermal Evolution of ZnS Nanostructures: Effect of Oxidation Phenomena on Structural Features and Photocatalytical Performances. *Inorganic Chemistry* **2018**, *57* (21), 13104-13114.
- (22) Mahdizadeh, R., et al., Surface texture dependency of photocatalytic behavior of facile synthesized mesoporous ZnS-ZnO heterostructure under LED illumination. *Sci Rep* **2025**, *15* (1), 30272.
- (23) Dethlefsen, J. R.; Døssing, A., Preparation of a ZnS Shell on CdSe Quantum Dots Using a Single-Molecular ZnS Precursor. *Nano Lett.* **2011**, *11* (5), 1964-1969.
- (24) Nedelcu, G., et al., Fast Anion-Exchange in Highly Luminescent Nanocrystals of Cesium Lead Halide Perovskites (CsPbX₃, X = Cl, Br, I). *Nano Lett.* **2015**, *15* (8), 5635-5640.
- (25) Ali, A., et al., Enhanced band edge luminescence of ZnO nanorods after surface passivation with ZnS. *Physica E: Low-dimensional Systems and Nanostructures* **2018**, *103*, 329-337.
- (26) Binetti, E., et al., Tuning light emission of PbS nanocrystals from infrared to visible range by cation exchange. *Science and Technology of Advanced Materials* **2015**, *16* (5), 055007.
- (27) Egerton, R. F., *Electron Energy-Loss Spectroscopy in the Electron Microscope* 3ed.; Springer New York, NY, 2011; p 491.
- (28) Yu, Z., et al., Shell Distribution on Colloidal CdSe/ZnS Quantum Dots. *Nano Lett.* **2005**, *5* (4), 565-570.
- (29) Fernández-Delgado, N., et al., Structural and chemical characterization of CdSe-ZnS core-shell quantum dots. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2018**, *457*, 93-97.
- (30) Fernández-Delgado, N., et al., HAADF-STEM for the analysis of core-shell quantum dots. *Journal of Materials Science* **2018**, *53* (21), 15226-15236.
- (31) Rice, K. P., et al., Seed-Mediated Growth of Shape-Controlled Wurtzite CdSe Nanocrystals: Platelets, Cubes, and Rods. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135* (17), 6669-6676.
- (32) Karim, M. R., et al., Strain Effects on the Band Gap and Diameter of CdSe Core and CdSe/ZnS Core/Shell Quantum Dots at Any Temperature. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering* **2019**, *2019* (1), 3764395.
- (33) Pisheh, H. S., et al., The effects of strain and spacer layer in CdSe/CdS/ZnS and CdSe/ZnS/CdS core/shell quantum dots. *Physica E: Low-dimensional Systems and Nanostructures* **2017**, *85*, 334-339.